

LAO

MINES ADVISORY GROUP

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GROUP

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HUMANITARIAN MINE ACTION

Right: A victim of curiosity.

In October 1998, Chanh and his younger brother Thoy were nearly killed when an object that they found exploded. They had picked up the shiny metal cylinder when digging for potatoes near their home. Their parents were out – their mother visiting relatives in another village, their father at work in the nearby town of Phonsavanh. At home alone, they played with their new toy unaware that it was the sensitive fuse from an artillery shell. It exploded in Thoy's hand, ripping off his fingers. Both boys are scarred by the tiny metal fragments into which the fuse disintegrated.

In hospital, a few days later, Thoy sits with his mother. The shock of the experience is clear in his expressionless face and glazed eyes. His mother says the accident happened when the boys were outside digging. She is embarrassed that it could have happened out of ignorance and won't admit that they had picked the item up.

Introduction

The Lao People's Democratic Republic (Lao PDR), in the heart of South East Asia, provides a frightening example of the long-term impact of remote, mechanised war on civilian populations. Whilst landmines have been stigmatised internationally for their crippling impact on civilian communities after conflict, the capacity for other unexploded ordnance (UXO) to continue killing and to restrict social and economic development is less well understood. The Lao government's unexploded ordnance authority, UXO LAO, is working in partnership with specialist non-governmental organisations (NGOs), and the United Nations (UN), to address the lethal remnants of a conflict that finished some 25 years ago.

From 1965 to 1973, the Pathet Lao and North Vietnamese fought against the Royal Lao Army and the Hmong irregulars sponsored by the USA. The ground fighting between these forces has left a significant legacy of unexploded land-service ammunition – mortars, artillery shells, grenades and the like. However, it was the secret aerial bombardment of Lao by the United States of America that has resulted in an unprecedented scale of unexploded ordnance contamination. In support of its Hmong allies, and in an effort to break the logistical artery of the Ho Chi Minh Trail running down Lao's eastern border, America undertook one of the largest aerial bombardments in the history of warfare. Per head of population, Lao is perhaps the most heavily bombed country on earth and, as a result, the Lao

people must live amongst massive quantities of unexploded ordnance and military scrap.

Such is the scale of UXO contamination that, as communities have rebuilt their physical, social and economic structures in the wake of this war, military debris has become an integral part of everyday life. Ordnance has been transformed into lamps (see cover photo) and forged into sickles and knives, other military debris is converted into chairs, boats and stilts for houses. But this resource also causes death, injury, fear and impoverishment, and stifles plans for social and economic development. Digging the land, making a fire and cutting through undergrowth are all dangerous tasks in many parts of Lao PDR. Land use for agriculture cannot be safely extended and construction projects cannot be undertaken without locating and destroying unexploded ordnance.

UXO contamination presents a barrier to the long-term development of Lao PDR. With support from the United Nations, NGOs and international donors, the Lao government has built a capacity to tackle this contamination through skilled and experienced Lao staff. In 1994, MAG was the first NGO to undertake the training and deployment of Lao ordnance disposal and 'community awareness' teams. Today, five years on, MAG is planning to hand-over these teams to the control of UXO LAO, an organisation that, given international support, will carry this work into the future.

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UNEXPLODED ORDNANCE (UXO) AND EXPLOSIVE ORDNANCE DISPOSAL (EOD).

In any conflict, a significant proportion of ammunition that is fired, or ordnance that is used, fails to explode as intended. These unexploded but unstable items remain buried in the ground or lying on the surface. Depending on the reason for their initial failure, the type of ordnance, and the physical and chemical effects of lying in the environment for a number of years, these items can detonate if touched, moved or tampered with. The danger of detonating UXO also makes construction projects and extending land use dangerous. Because of this, increasing agricultural productivity, developing social-services and economic or industrial projects can be made difficult or impossible in contaminated areas.

The clearance of UXO is called Explosive Ordnance Disposal (EOD). MAG trains teams to locate and destroy unexploded ordnance. Locating UXO is done either on the basis of sightings by the local community, or by searching the ground with metal detectors. Ordnance that is found is destroyed under controlled conditions to ensure the safety of local people, their property and livestock, as well as MAG's own staff.

An unexploded 2000lb US aircraft bomb, near to the school in Saravane town, southern Lao PDR. MAG has located over 500 such big bombs in Saravane Province (see page 16.)

Overview

Xieng Khouang project staff:

110 Technicians
(4 Roving Teams, up to
8 Clearance Teams)
21 Community Awareness staff
(1 Contact Team, 3 CA Teams,
1 Follow-up Team)
11 Medics
16 Drivers
24 Local management and support staff
Total staff: 182

Xieng Khouang Province, in the north-central highlands of Lao, was the scene of extensive ground-fighting between the Royal Lao Army and the Pathet Lao and People's Army of North Vietnam, as well as heavy aerial bombardment by the United States of America.

MAG's project in Xieng Khouang started in 1994 in partnership with the Mennonite Central Committee. In 1997, according to UXO LAO statistics, the MAG project in Xieng Khouang was responsible for the destruction of 72% of the total amount of ordnance destroyed in Lao PDR.

The people of Xieng Khouang province continue to suffer from the highest number of UXO related accidents in the country – in 1998 there were 81 victims, an apparent increase on the previous 3 years. This is probably due to the more effective accident reporting system that has been established in Xieng Khouang and the expansion of activities from three main districts to all six districts of the province.

MAG has a permanent expatriate presence of 2 Technical Advisors in Xieng Khouang and some 90% of demolitions are now conducted without expatriate supervision. With the opening of the Management School in 1999, MAG is undertaking the administrative and managerial capacity building that will allow the programme to be handed over to UXO LAO in 2001.

Saravane project staff (projected for Sept 99):

90 Technicians (4 Roving Teams,
up to 8 Clearance Teams)
12 Community Awareness staff
(1 Contact Team, 2 CA Teams,
1 Follow-up Team)
12 Medics
12 Drivers

MAG began work in Saravane Province at the end of 1997. The work is split between three operations bases – Saravane town, Ta Oi and Samuoi.

Ground fighting and aerial bombardment have left a wide range of unexploded ordnance in the vicinity of Saravane town – from land service ammunition to large aircraft bombs.

The eastern districts of Saravane Province, towards the border with Vietnam, are mountainous jungle with difficult roads and scattered populations. During the Vietnam conflict, the Ho Chi Minh trail network ran north-south through this area and the USA undertook continuous bombing in an effort to stop the flow of supplies into South Vietnam. This history is reflected in the large quantities of air-dropped ordnance that MAG is destroying in Ta Oi and Samuoi Districts.

MAG plans to expand into a fourth district of Saravane from September 1999. From September 1999, all national staff in Saravane will become employees of UXO LAO.

Lao Chronology:

1893 France colonises the area east of the Mekong now known as Lao PDR.

1945 Lao declares independence following France's defeat at Dien Bien Phu. A "neutralist" royal parliamentary regime backed by France and the US is established in Vientiane.

1955 Laos joins the United Nations.

1955 Lao People's Revolutionary Party (LPRP) is formally established.

1963 Armed struggle of the Pathet Lao starts and lasts until 1973 when a coalition government is formed.

1964-1973 Heavy aerial bombardment of Laos by the USA.

1975 LPRP assumes full power and Lao Peoples Democratic Republic (Lao PDR) is founded.

1986 New Economic Mechanism adopted.

1994 MAG begins the first programme to destroy unexploded ordnance in Xieng Khouang Province, in partnership with the Mennonite Central Committee (MCC).

1995 A partnership between the Lao Government, UNDP and UNICEF establishes the Lao Trust Fund to raise and manage money for ordnance eradication.

1996 UXO LAO is established to coordinate ordnance eradication efforts and to develop a national capacity to perpetuate this work.

1997 Lao PDR joins the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN). MAG begins a second programme in Saravane Province.

Victims of the bombing – facts and figures:

In Xieng Khouang Province some 45% of accidents have occurred as a result of the deliberate handling of UXO.
Across the country, substantially more accidents occur to men than to women.
From 1973-1996, 86% of accident victims have been men or boys.

(Statistics from 1997 National Study on the Socio-economic Impact of Unexploded Ordnance)

The bombing of Laos – facts and figures:

Between 1964 and 1973, the US flew 580,344 bombing missions over northern and southern Laos.
Just over 2 million tons of bombs were dropped during this period.
The average cost of the bombing was \$2,190,000 per day.

(Statistics from the Mennonite Central Committee)

CAMBODIA

UNEXPLODED UXO ORDNANCE

Even small items of ordnance, through fragmentation and a powerful explosive charge, are capable of claiming many victims in a single explosion. In January 1998, Xieng Khouang Province, seven children were killed and another was seriously injured when a bomblet that they had found exploded. These bomblets are no bigger than a clenched fist.

KEY ISSUES:

- ◆ What are cluster bombs?
- ◆ The unpredictability of unexploded ordnance.
- ◆ Some common Lao beliefs about the dangers of UXO.
- ◆ UXO and military debris as part of everyday life.

Cluster bombs

MAG has encountered over 100 different types of UXO in Lao PDR. Of these, anti-personnel 'bomblets' are responsible for some 50% of ordnance accidents in the two Provinces where MAG works. Bomblets are the individual weapons that are packed together in air-dropped cluster bombs. Cluster bombs may each contain as many as 670 bomblets. There are some 12 different types of bomblet commonly found in Lao PDR.

Cluster bombs were the weapon of choice for attacking personnel and convoys from the air. All of the different types of bomblets rely on 'fragmentation' as their principle method of wounding. Upon detonation, the bomblet's casing breaks up into small metal fragments. These fragments, propelled by the force of the explosion, cut through the surrounding area at ballistic speed. The fragmentation from a single bomblet explosion may create a danger area with a radius of up to 150m. Some bomblets also contain an 'anti-material' component in addition to fragmentation. This will create an incendiary effect to set fire to vehicles and buildings, as well as people.

Bomblets are aerodynamically designed so that they spread out in the air. This ensures that the explosive con-

tents of the cluster bomb cover a broad area by the time they strike their targets. Spreading out the bomblets also further extends the large 'killing area' created by each bomblet on detonation.

There are a massive number of bomblets lying unexploded across Lao PDR. Their small size and regular shape, make them particularly attractive to children. Some bomblets are brightly coloured, making them even more interesting and eye-catching for children.

MAG has destroyed over 430 bomblets from around Boun Pheng's house and garden.

"I knew that there were bomblets here because I found some when I was building my house. But I didn't know that there were so many – they even found one under my bed."

MAG has searched the area with detectors to ensure that all of the ordnance has been removed. The large number of bomblets found in such a small area is probably the result of a cluster-bomb being dropped too low, giving the bomblets insufficient time in the air to become armed.

Diagram: A cluster bomb opens in the air, allowing the individual explosive 'bomblets' to spread out over the target.

Whilst the empty casings are used as building materials in many parts of Lao PDR, unexploded bomblets are still claiming innocent lives.

An unpredictable legacy

All items of UXO are unpredictable. There is generally no way to tell how dangerous an individual item actually is. Although the outer casing may have degraded over time the fuse can be in pristine working condition. Some bomblets had delay fuses, to arm them only after hitting the ground. Others, such as the BLU42, were air-dropped antipersonnel mines, ejecting trip-wires on striking the ground and lying in wait for victims.

Many anti-personnel bomblets were

designed to become armed as a result of the spinning motion of the bomblet in the air. If they did not have time to achieve the necessary rate of revolutions as they fell to earth, the bomblet would fail to detonate because it was unarmed. Unarmed bomblets can be lying amongst armed bomblets that have not exploded because of some other mishap in the way they landed. Even some unarmed bomblets may be detonated if struck with sufficient force. Other bomblets, such as the BLU 26, may be armed but fail to explode because the delay mechanism has become jammed. A subsequent disturbance could restart the delay mechanism, once again starting the count-down to detonation. This range of different examples provides an indication of how difficult it is to determine the current status of an individual item and how it came to lie unexploded so long after the conflict.

In 1997, two men were killed and four others were seriously injured when an artillery shell exploded at a blacksmiths forge. The blacksmith had been using the base of the artillery shell as an anvil – believing it was safe because the fuse had been removed. Next to the forge for several months, the shell had been repeatedly heated and cooled without incident. On 10 February it exploded.

This sort of unpredictability means that people have a range of potentially conflicting experiences, either first-hand or from others, of the results that can be expected from contact with ordnance. This has allowed a wide range of beliefs to develop regarding the safety of different types of UXO – beliefs that vary from one community to the next.

In Xieng Khouang, many villagers express a belief that the more corroded a piece of UXO, the less dangerous it is. This has resulted in practices such as pouring salt on UXO, urinating on it, or depositing it in water to accelerate decomposition. In fact, corrosion can actually make an item of UXO more likely to function.

Villagers generally feel that bomblets can be moved relatively safely, as long as the item is picked up and carried without changing its orientation and without any violent movement.

Some villagers have gained prestige from their ability to dismantle items of UXO. If several dismantlers are killed over a period of time in one village, the remaining dismantlers achieve even greater expert status by virtue of the fact that they are still alive.

This confusion of ideas and attitudes, in an environment where ordnance is so common, demands that as well as destroying UXO, efforts should be made to develop, within communities, a general rule that ordnance should be feared. This is especially true when we consider that the most common causes of accidents involve deliberate contact, such as children playing with UXO or adults trying to extract the explosives.

LIVING WITH UXO

The aerial bombardment of Lao can be seen as an effort to destroy the very fabric of life in areas of the country controlled by Pathet Lao and North Vietnamese forces. As communities have rebuilt themselves in the aftermath of this onslaught, the residue of unexploded ordnance and military debris has become part of this fabric. As a threat and as a resource, the remnants of war have become part of a complex pattern of fear, need and utility.

Rural populations in many parts of Lao PDR have had nearly a quarter of a century to adjust to living with UXO. Providing a wide range of raw metal or pre-fabricated items, this debris is one of the most important resources freely available in the local environment. Although the trade in scrap metal has declined since its peak in the mid-1980s, and has been outlawed by the Lao government, the use of military debris for an incredible range of practical purposes continues unabated.

The Blacksmith

The workshop and house of a blacksmith in Ban Soy village, Xieng Khouang Province, provides an illustration of these issues. Mr Sopha, the blacksmith, relies on military debris for the implements that he fashions. His small workshop has bellows and anvils under the cover of a thatched roof supported by the empty casings of American cluster bombs.

“I have been working this way as a blacksmith since the end of the war, so for 25 years now. I always use bits from bombs and shells that have exploded – I don’t use live bombs or bombs which still have their fuzes anymore because I am too afraid. Artillery shells are the best – the metal is harder and stronger and keeps a sharp blade for longer. I just use scrap metal that I find – sometimes people bring metal to me. I buy cluster bomb

Mortar bombs and rockets help to hold down the thatched roof during storms.

casing to make shovels but knives and sickles are what I make the most.”

The anvils on which the knives are fashioned are the bases of artillery shells protruding from the ground.

“I make a big stock of knives and sickles and then a relative in Phonsavanh takes them across to Vientiane to sell. They sell for 3000kip each retail or 2000kip wholesale. This is only part-time work though. There are 10 people in my family here and we farm rice paddy and keep poultry and cattle. The knife sales are very important for raising us extra money to buy clothes, food, goods for the house or more cattle.”

The blacksmith’s family live in the house next to his forge. As well as providing a means to generate additional income, ordnance has a wide range of roles in the home. Cooking for the family relies heavily on reclaimed ordnance. Pico-bamboo soup simmers in a pot made from an artillery shell, it is stirred with an aluminium spoon that has been fashioned from an artillery cartridge. Pots are supported above the fire on a frame of recoilless-rifle rounds. Having been used by the family in these roles for some 22 years, it is not surprising that these are not thought of as items of military debris but merely as mundane household objects.

In the main living room of the house, an American cluster bomb munition has pride of place on the table (cover photo). The BLU 3/B bomblet, that has been converted into a paraffin lamp, was given to the blacksmith’s wife, Granny Ohn, by a relative in Phonsavanh. The conversion of this type of bomblet into lamps has become quite common. This reflects a local belief that the BLU 3/B is less dangerous to dismantle than other bomblets.

The familiarity of military debris to rural populations of Lao PDR provides a frightening indication of the scale of the conflict inflicted upon these areas. It is also a great barrier to reducing the number of UXO accidents. The bulk of ordnance related accidents result from people making deliberate contact with UXO. That such contact is socially acceptable, and economically valuable, makes it very hard to counteract.

Boats fashioned out of USAF fighter-bomber fuel tanks.

Bombs outside a chemist shop in Phonsavanh.

Mr Sopha hammering the blade of a knife. His anvil is the base of an artillery shell and the photograph is framed by one of the fragmentation damaged cluster-bomb casings that support the roof of his forge.

UXO LAO

LAO PDR NATIONAL CAPACITY

With assistance from the United Nations and a number of international NGOs, the Lao Government has developed an impressive capacity to undertake the task of ordnance eradication. UXO LAO, part of the Ministry of Labour and Social Welfare, coordinates and implements explosive ordnance disposal across Lao PDR. UXO LAO has grown rapidly and now provides an important model for how the work of ordnance and landmine eradication can be centrally structured and organised to address local development needs.

Mr Bounpone Sayasenh, Director of UXO LAO:

"The 1997 survey of the impact of UXO in Lao PDR, which was carried out by Handicap International, found that there had been around 11,000 UXO accidents from 1973 to 1996. As well as these accidents, rural people are kept poor because they are afraid to increase the land that they have for agricultural production and development. The Lao government saw the need to find donors and assistance from outside – so as to help people to live safely and increase the land that they have to use.

MAG took the initiative in Xieng Khouang Province in 1994. The Lao government had no experience and no resources for this kind of work. MAG's project in Xieng Khouang was well respected and seen as a programme that could be expanded. Seeing that this kind of project could really help people, we had discussions with UNDP and UNICEF to establish the Lao Trust Fund in 1995. UXO LAO was then set-up in 1996.

In 1996, UXO LAO covered just three Provinces, in 1997 this increased to eight Provinces and at the end of 1998 we are

working across nine Provinces. The project has progressed well and expanded rapidly.

Because of the bombing here, the amounts of UXO in Lao are massive and we will have to carry out this work for many years. This makes it very important to prioritise what we do to ensure that it is the most helpful work for the local people. Plans for irrigation, village building and increasing agricultural productivity may all need EOD work to support them and allow them to happen.

This year, our Provincial Coordinators and our NGO partners must prepare and have their work-plans approved before they are submitted to UXO LAO. This means that the plans are linked to what provincial leaders want for their local communities. The provincial authorities are the people that we are working for in terms of prioritising work – they know what the development needs are for their local areas. UXO LAO has advised provincial leaders and NGOs to work together – to solve problems and discuss their concerns so as to best help the Lao people."

UXO LAO is now working with 6 NGO partners who provide technical advice to the EOD Teams in the field. The relationship between UXO LAO and these partners suggests how international NGOs can work with government institutions to provide the most effective response to problems of post-war ordnance contamination. An important role for these NGOs has been the capacity building work that will allow ever increasing Lao control over all aspects of the ordnance eradication programme.

"It is not a problem for us working with many different NGOs. They have their own systems but UXO LAO is

KEY ISSUES:

- ◆ Building a national capacity through partnership.
- ◆ Linking ordnance eradication to local development needs.
- ◆ Skilled and experienced Lao staff – a capacity for the future.

organising and working with all of them. We understand that the NGOs have their own systems but we need to standardise in order to make our work as effective and sustainable as possible.

Sometimes NGOs want to work more independently but it is very important for us that they work with the cooperation of the local authorities. Although sometimes

After working for MAG, Kampat (pointing) is now a senior instructor for UXO LAO at Ban Y Lai training school near to Vientiane. Before making this transition he was optimistic about the growing capacity for Lao trainers to be training Lao staff:

"Training is very important so that MAG and UXO LAO staff can work well and do this work themselves. I don't think it will be difficult to make the transition to working for UXO LAO because they have the same objectives as MAG. We want to get rid of the UXO problem to make more land available for agriculture and services, and to reduce the numbers of people killed or injured."

Mr Bounpone Sayasenh, Director of UXO LAO, with a map of ordnance eradication programmes being undertaken across the country.

difficult, all of these problems can be solved. UXO LAO has talked to both groups to develop understanding – to get people to sit and discuss the issues together.

As well as working with the NGOs, we have a bilateral agreement with the USA. They provide training and equipment. At the training centre we now have

Lao trainers working with all the US staff. We hope that much of this training work will be done by Lao staff in the future.

The basis of our programme is capacity building for local staff. This is already happening with Lao instructors doing more and more training work. MAG in Xieng Khouang has reduced the number of expatriate Technical Advisors because

Lao staff are taking more and more responsibility. MAG is planning to hand over the Xieng Khouang Programme to UXO LAO over the next few years.

Responsibility, ownership and partnership are very important to us. The Lao capacity to eradicate the UXO is growing stronger all the time because of the partnerships that we have developed.”

MAG LAO

KEY ISSUES:

- ◆ MAG's work in Lao PDR is structured in two separate sections:
- ◆ Information Gathering, Community Awareness and Roving Teams work together to respond to the immediate needs for ordnance eradication and education amongst local communities – reducing the risks they face.
- ◆ Clearance Teams work to the priorities established in partnership with the Provincial Authorities. Clearance Teams allow the development of social and economic facilities such as schools, clinics and agricultural land.

Information Gathering

Information on the problems faced by different communities provides a basis for prioritising the work of MAG's Community Awareness and Roving Teams. However, gathering this information can be hampered by the difficulties of transport and language – particularly in Saravane Province. Boun You, from MAG's Community Awareness Survey Team, covers difficult terrain every day:

"The roads here are very bad which makes it hard to reach people living in remote villages. Often we have to walk for more than an hour from one village to

another because even our motorbikes cannot go any further. Villagers have often heard of MAG and are usually very happy when we arrive. The most important thing is that we explain who we are and what we are doing. When they understand what we are trying to do people are happy to give us their support. The villagers provide very good accommodation. They always find us a bed to sleep in and share their food with us."

The local language presents a barrier even to staff who have been recruited from this area.

"The language is still a problem. I understand only about 30% of the local languages spoken in Saravane Province. When we are talking to people and trying to make a map of UXO in their area we need help from local people who can translate from their language into a language that I can understand."

In Samouï District, where MAG has an operations base, it is estimated that only around 5% of the population speak the Lao national language.

Above: Data gatherers cross a river near Saravane. Travelling around this jungle clad mountainous region can be very difficult and often they have to resort to walking from village to village

Right: Puppet shows bring to life the social issues surrounding contact with UXO. They illustrate how peer-group pressure can cause accidents and also portray the emotional impact of UXO accidents on surviving family members.

Community Awareness

The information gathered on the levels of ordnance contamination in local villages determines the priorities for the next stage of MAG's work – community education and mapping the UXO that has been found.

In an environment so saturated with unexploded ordnance, and where people have no choice but to live and work around the problem, MAG's community awareness programme emphasises practical steps that can be taken to make dangerous activities safer:

- ◆ Cut vegetation higher up the stem, some 20-30 cm above the ground. Cutting vegetation is best done with a horizontal movement of the blade, rather than a blow down towards the ground.
- ◆ Lao people often use a hoe to break up the ground – striking the earth from above their head. Shovels are safer to use, especially when cultivating new ground.

- ◆ UXO buried in the soil can be detonated if fires are made on the ground above it. Pile up earth to provide a safe base on which to build fires.
- ◆ Tether animals to trees rather than driving stakes into the ground to tie them to.
- ◆ Lao farmers often burn off existing vegetation when preparing land for cultivation. Stand well away from areas where forest or scrub is being burnt.

In addition to its own teams, MAG works in partnership with Consortium and UNICEF to distribute these messages through teachers and over the radio.

The Community Awareness Teams also hold village meetings to discuss and map the location of known items of UXO in the immediate environment. These meetings involve all members of the community and provide a basis of information that will be used by the Roving Team when they visit the village in the near future.

KEY ISSUES:

- ◆ Reducing the immediate risk to the community.
- ◆ Responding to emergency needs.
- ◆ The range of ordnance that MAG's teams destroy.

Roving Teams

Most accidents are caused by ordnance lying on the surface – particularly children playing with items that they find. By tackling this problem, MAG's Roving Teams are reducing the immediate risk of accidents around the community.

Roving Teams use the information gathered during Community Awareness Team visits to a village. Utilising the map that the Community Awareness Team have drawn, the Roving Team works its way through the village's local environment destroying the items that have been identified. The work around a community can cover a wide area; land used for farming, grazing cattle or collecting wood may be some 6km from the village centre.

Roving Teams also respond to emergency tasks. In both Saravane and Xieng Khouang, almost all buildings were destroyed by the bombing. The buildings that have been constructed in these areas

since the war have been built on potentially contaminated land. MAG receives regular requests for assistance when people uncover items of ordnance whilst building houses or establishing gardens.

These teams tackle an extensive range of ordnance. Although American air-dropped ordnance accounts for some 75% of the items that MAG destroys, land-service ammunition has been found originating from China, the former Soviet Union, Vietnam, USA and France. In one former ammunition dump in Saravane town, MAG even unearthed one of the first models of anti-tank rifle grenade, developed by the British during World War II. The huge number of items that MAG's Roving Teams have destroyed, and the range of ordnance in the country, has helped to build an experienced body of staff that will be a valuable resource for UXO LAO in the future.

Above: The Senior Technician from one of MAG's Roving Teams works marks and maps ordnance whilst on secondment to a Community Awareness Team.

Top Right: The Roving Team goes in search of unexploded ordnance. The box held by the leading team member is the 'exploder' that is used to detonate the demolition charges down an electrical cable. Behind him, team members carry loud-hailers for clearing people away from the area of the demolition and firing cable for initiating the explosives from a safe distance.

Far right: Roving Team medics unpack stretchers and medical equipment. Specially trained medics are present whenever MAG conducts ordnance disposal work.

Right: Discussing the location of UXO around a village with community leaders. The cooperation of local people is vital at all stages of MAG's work.

Clearance Teams

Clearance Teams search the ground with detectors to uncover ordnance buried under the surface. The levels of contamination in Lao PDR are so great that this approach is only practical on very high priority land. In addition to a large number of school sites, MAG has cleared land for a wide range of other projects. Particularly in Xieng Khouang, MAG is clearing areas of agricultural land to assist food production in the province.

Boun Doup school

Boun Doup is a village of some 450 people on the former Ho Chi Minh Trail, near to MAG's operations base at Ta Oi, Saravane Province. The village stands in a clearing on what was an intersection in the Vietnamese supply route south. Thong Chan, one of the older women in the village, remembers men destroying ordnance when they were rebuilding the village:

"During the war the people here lived in tunnels and caves in the forest. It seemed like the bombing never stopped. When it was time to rebuild the village, families came back who had lived here before. After the bombing there was nothing left of this village – there were just craters, broken trees and lots of scrap left behind by the bombing and the Vietnamese soldiers."

"There was lots of unexploded ordnance around here after the war. Some of it was destroyed by building fires around it or it was carried into the jungle. I remember men putting ordnance in pits to be burned. They did this so that the explosion went up away from the people. There is still ordnance under the ground – like the bombies that are at the school."

The small school is a simple thatched roof supported on the casings of USAF cluster bombs. Elsewhere in the village cluster bomb cases are used to grow veg-

etables and as nurseries for fruit trees. As in so many villages in this area, rice stores are also mounted on these cases – the smooth curved metal is almost impossible for vermin to climb.

A new school is being built at Boun Doup to accommodate children from nearby villages which, at present, have no education facilities. The ethnic dialects in this area have no written form and very few people speak the Lao national language. As a result, literacy levels are extremely low. Improved education is vital if these populations are to be given better access to healthcare information and other social services.

MAG has found more than ten bomblets whilst clearing land for this project. The local people had seen bomblets lying on the surface and the district authorities recognised that the site needed to be cleared in order for the school development programme to go ahead.

The old school at Boun Doup. Children are warned of the dangers of unexploded ordnance in a classroom supported by cluster bomb casings. MAG is clearing ordnance from the ground nearby so that a larger school can be built.

Khan Khai teacher training college

At Khan Khai, Xieng Khouang Province, MAG has been working to support the expansion of a teacher training college. Money for the college has been provided by the Asia Development Bank and the project is part of the developing social service plans for Xieng Khouang Province.

As the Head of the Office of Teaching Improvements explains, the rationale behind the project is simple:

“In the past the college has been able to train around 300 students per year but with the new expansion this will increase to 400 students. This expansion is very important because this college provides teachers for the whole of 2 provinces. This is very important but in Xieng Khouang, and in many other parts of Lao PDR, you cannot expand facilities such as this without clearing the land of ordnance.”

Some 25% of the land area of Xieng Khouang is thought to be heavily contaminated with UXO. So far, MAG has found and destroyed 114 bomblets and 888 other items of ordnance at this site. Whilst rural populations live with the fear of ordnance in their own environment, they also want greater access and improvements to education and medical facilities. According to the UN Country Strategy Note of 1996, one third of primary school teachers have not been trained at a teacher training college. The construction of village schools and clinics often requires land to be cleared of ordnance before building work can commence. As the example of Khan Khai training college illustrates, even providing trained staff for these facilities can require an extensive ordnance eradication project.

Clearing UXO at Khan Khai teacher training college. Projects such as this are planned between UXO LAO's NGO partners and their Provincial Coordinators. In this way, the broad development plans of the individual provinces are represented in the prioritisation of ordnance clearance work.

New techniques on trial

MAG is also working to clear agricultural land that will be used for food production to support Khan Khai college. On this site, a new approach to detecting ordnance is being tested. MAG is using an Ebinger UPEX 740M 'large-loop' detector as the first search tool. This detector will locate items deeper underground but can discriminate between larger and smaller amounts of metal. Clearance proceeds more quickly because the 'large-loop' does not register as much scrap metal as the traditional detector and, therefore, there are less signals for the technicians to investigate.

This method has the potential to clear a lot more land of bomblets and other ordnance. Now that MAG's staff are experienced with the detector, they are

able to cover some 1,000m² in a full day's work.

Signals that are picked up by the large loop detector are marked by the technicians to be investigated by other staff with more sensitive detectors at a later stage. The large-loop is kept moving all day in order to cover the ground as efficiently as possible. Only when the large loop detector has moved a sufficient distance away for the work to be done safely does the second team begin the investigation with traditional, more sensitive, detectors.

MAG believes that the 'large-loop' detector will be able to increase significantly the rate at which ordnance contaminated agricultural land can be brought back to productive use.

BIG BOMBS

In Saravane Province alone, MAG has located more than 500 unexploded large bombs, each weighing between 100 and 3,000 lbs. In Taoi District some 28 large bombs have been recorded in just one village. MAG began the destruction of these bombs with the removal and demolition of three 3,000 lb bombs that were situated within Saravane town – one was in the garden next door to the MAG office.

Large unexploded aircraft bombs present considerable difficulties to destroy because of the large area that will be affected by the explosion. Arrangements are made well in advance to ensure that people and their animals can be moved to safety. Nearby villages must also be warned to prevent people from moving into the danger area from outside. Notice of the planned demolitions is given over the radio and the television. Despite these efforts, MAG must also work around the realities of village life: people can fall ill and be unfit to be moved regardless of how far in advance a demolition has been planned.

It is always assumed that some people will not know what is being planned. Sentries walk out from the bomb to their positions at the perimeter of the safety-cordon. Using loud-hailers to explain what is happening, they positively check that the area is clear of people. Establishing a safety-cordon with a radius that may be in excess of a kilometre is extremely difficult, especially where visibility may be poor due to dense vegetation or hilly terrain. More than one Roving Team is needed to provide enough sentries to ensure that the area is clear of people. In many parts of Saravane Province, the jungle is so dense and widespread that villages are almost invisible until you enter them. This is a problem for all demolitions and means that MAG's Roving Teams in Saravane Province work more slowly than their counterparts in Xieng Khouang. Also in

Saravane, the range of local dialects can sometimes make it difficult to communicate warnings effectively.

'Low order techniques' present an alternative to the full detonation of big bombs. Although these techniques are used to avoid a full detonation – and so reduce damage to surrounding property – safety procedures and evacuations are always carried out on the assumption that a full detonation will take place. 'Low order techniques' serve to make the dis-

posal of big bombs safer and of a lesser impact on the surrounding environment. These techniques do however rely on the availability of good information about the fusing mechanisms of individual items of ordnance. Some of the ordnance dropped on Lao is still in service with the USAF and, as a result, the relevant information about Render Safe Procedures is unfortunately still classified. This lack of information is hampering the work of ordnance eradication in Lao PDR.

Conclusion

A 2000lb aircraft bomb lies unexploded in the grounds of a Wat in Saravane town. A number of years ago, the local monks rolled the bomb into this gully, away from their living quarters.

The problem of UXO in Lao is so severe because of the type of war that was waged on the country and the nature of the weapons used. A bombing of unprecedented scale failed to achieve its overarching strategic objectives and was conducted with no regard for its long-term impact on the civilian population. The extensive use of cluster bombs greatly increased the number of individual explosive items and, therefore, the quantities of UXO. That the extent and

nature of the war in Lao remain little known to many people in the West is an alarming consequence of the secretive way in which it was conducted. It would compound this tragedy further if the impact of this bombing on the long-term development of Lao PDR was not appreciated by the broader international community.

Whilst landmines and before them chemical and biological weapons have been stigmatised internationally, the relationship between air-dropped ordnance and the post-conflict environment has received less public attention. Some governments have suggested that they cannot fund ordnance eradication in Lao PDR because the problem does not fall under the scope of the Ottawa Convention, which bans anti-personnel landmines and requires support for their eradication. The spirit of the Ottawa Convention was not to limit assistance to post-conflict communities by rigidly proscribing the form of technical contamination from which they must be suffering in order to merit assistance. UXO contamination must be addressed in accordance with the problems that it is causing and will continue to cause.

The development of UXO LAO and its work in partnership with the United Nations and international NGOs is a strong positive model for the organisation and implementation of efforts to eradicate the UXO problem. The integration of local political authorities into the prioritisation process of UXO LAO is very important. It not only means that work is conducted with a good local perspective but also suggests how UXO LAO's work has become part of the broader administrative system of the country. This is particularly important because the scale of bombardment that this country suffered ensures that unexploded ordnance eradication will be an important task for the Lao government well into the next century.

MAG would like to thank the donors who are funding this work, notably:

- ◆ Anti-Landmijn Stichting (Netherlands)
- ◆ CIDSE
- ◆ DFID – Department for International Development (UK)
- ◆ The Danish Government (through Danida)
- ◆ Douglas and Audrey Miller
- ◆ Oxfam Hong Kong

MAG needs funding that will allow it to respond to the real needs of landmine and UXO-affected populations. Credit card donations can be made on:

0800 0723 999

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Produced by MAG, May 1999.

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